

INFLUENCE OF PARENTING STYLES ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN PRE-PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN NORTH WEST NIGERIA

Gidado, Bello Kumo, Apeh, Hosea Abalaka and Tanko, Linus

Department of Educational Foundations, University of Abuja, Nigeria

10.5281/zenodo.17525415

ABSTRACT: This study investigates the influence of parenting style on conduct disorder and academic performance among pre-primary school pupils in the North-West region of Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey research design, guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The research population consisted of 184,682 pre-primary school pupils from 9,382 public pre-primary schools in the North-West region of Nigeria. A sample size of 400 was used in the study employing a proportionate random sampling technique. A structured survey questionnaire with a 4-point rating system was used to collect data. The instruments were validated, and a trial test was conducted to assess the reliability of the instrument. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the study hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that authoritarian parenting styles have no significant impact on academic performance. Similarly, it was found that authoritative and permissive parenting styles have a significant influence on the academic performance of pre-primary pupils. Based on the findings, recommendations were made that to enhance student outcomes, educators, legislators, and community leaders should advocate for authoritative parenting practices which promote caring and supportive relations. This can help parents become better instructors and role models to their children.

Keywords: Parenting Styles, Academic Performance, Pre-primary School

INTRODUCTION

Parents are typically the most critical people in a child's life. Parents are basically the well spring and fountain of every family, hence they are obligated or saddled with responsibilities such as economical, psychological, moral, spiritual which is aimed at improving their offspring and other members within the family unit which goes a long way in improving serenity, productivity and development of the society (Gidado & Diffang, 2023). Being successful or unsuccessful in life may be influenced by the lessons taught to children at home and how the family encourages them to pursue education and other goals. A child is a precursor of his home background, since every individual is from a family which in most cases influences their behavioural conducts (Gidado & Diffang, 2023). The child learns about the customs, traditions, values, and norms of the immediate environment within the context of their

family. Thus, parents play an essential role in nurturing children from all angles, including physical, emotional, social, moral, and educational aspects (Noreen, Ahmad, and Shahzadi, 2021).

Parenting style, which encompasses parental views and conduct, is a psychological pattern that describes the parenting tactics frequently used by parents in child-rearing practices (Janius et al., 2024). It refers to the techniques employed by parents to raise or nurture their children, equipping them with the necessary skills to function appropriately as citizens of a given society (Tanko, 2025). It is also similar to child-rearing practices. Mogadime et al. (2022) assert that a child's social and academic development is significantly influenced by the parenting style employed. Similarly, Meremu and Idoko (2021) demonstrated that a parent's parenting style can either positively or negatively impact a child's academic performance and behaviour.

Academic Journal of Current Research

An official Publication of Center for International Research Development

Double Blind Peer and Editorial Review International Referred Journal; Globally index

Available <https://cirdjournals.com/index.php/ajcr>; E-mail: journals@cirdjournals.com

Parenting styles yield various personality traits, as well as psychological, social, and emotional outcomes in children; they also result in different academic performances among children in school. To be successful in higher education and life, however, children and young adults need trusting, supporting, and caring relationships with their families, especially with their parents (Steinberg, 2022). Consequently, parenting styles have become a robust approach and a central topic of study in the field of education and parenting in contemporary times, due to their significant impact on the development of children's personality traits, as well as their social and academic achievements (Adaku & Anayo, 2021).

This development has been necessitated by the awareness that has been created over the years, emphasising the benefits of good parenting practices through the adoption of appropriate parenting styles and their impact on education, which many parents are beginning to acknowledge as an effective means of achieving success in life. Again, there exists ample evidence in the literature that suggests that parenting styles are correlated with children's school achievement. Dornbusch et al. (2017) found that inconsistency and mixed parenting styles are correlated with lower grades for adolescents. Likewise, Janius et al. (2024) indicated that parenting style is one of the significant contributors to students' academic performance in school.

Recognising the value of education in today's world, parents are encouraged to make positive efforts to ensure active participation in their wards' education, thereby equipping them with the capacity to be socially mobile in life. Adaku and Anayo (2021) indicated that although pupils are primarily the ones for whom curricula are designed, textbooks are written, and schools are built, parents are primarily held responsible for preparing pupils for learning, physically, psychologically, behaviourally, attitudinally, emotionally, and motivationally, to name a few. Without the appropriate parenting style, parental involvement and proactive preparation of the child in the areas mentioned above, the child is likely to perform poorly in school.

Several scholars have grouped parenting approaches into various categories. Three categories of parenting styles were distinguished by Janius et al. (2024): authoritative, authoritarian and permissive parenting styles. Numerous facets of a child's development, including self-esteem,

academic success, and emotional intelligence, are significantly influenced by parenting practices. According to Janius et al. (2023), authoritative parenting is well known for promoting a child's social, cognitive, and emotional development. The favourable outcomes of the authoritative method focus on respect for one another. However, the effects of both permissive and authoritarian parenting approaches on development vary and are frequently influenced by cultural circumstances (Hassan et al., 2022).

The National Commission for Colleges of Education's (NCCE) minimum standard requirements and learning objectives revealed that learners should possess both positive academic outcomes and social skills (NCCE, 2020). Academic competency is expected to involve, for instance, content mastery, creative thinking, and cognitive inquiry. Social competency is expected to include self-sufficiency and collaboration with peers and adults in positions of authority, such as educators. Differences in the parental experiences that children have at home are significantly linked with differences in academic performance (Janius et al., 2024). This correlation might exist because children acquire social norms, interaction patterns, and language and cognitive stimulation in the home environment, all of which they carry over into the classroom. Studies on the effects of different parenting philosophies reveal that while some parenting philosophies align with educational demands, others do not.

Several studies have shown that families with authoritative parents experience numerous benefits, including higher academic achievement (Okudo & Obumse, 2022; Meremu & Idoko, 2021; Adaku & Anayo, 2021). According to Okudo and Obumse (2022), authoritative parents exhibit high levels of warmth, autonomy granting, reasoning, monitoring, firm yet rational control, maturity demands, and nurturing. Additionally, Meremu and Idoko (2021) equally revealed that an authoritative parenting style had a favourable relationship with the academic achievement of senior secondary school students. Likewise, Gidado & Abubakar (2025) reported a similar result, indicating that adolescents raised in an authoritative environment experience superior academic success, fewer behavioural problems, and decreased internal distress compared to those raised in non-authoritarian settings. Noreen et al. (2021) also reveal that parents maintain a

bond of affection and encouragement towards children, display attachment, place an emphasis on rules and regulations, deny children any degree of autonomy, refrain from spoiling them, and hold their children's hands tightly. Similarly, Gidado and Anyio (2025) indicated a significant difference in aggression among secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria based on parenting style. It is therefore concluded that authoritative parents were very accommodating and responsive as they encouraged their children about the dangers associated with negative peer influence.

By contrast, coercion, emotional control, verbal aggression, and corporal discipline are more common among authoritarian parents than among non-authoritarian parents. In view of the above, Ogazie & Arungwa (2021) suggest, in their research, that a strong negative association exists between authoritarian parenting style and pupils' academic success. Gidado & Abubakar (2025) also found a significant correlation between authoritarian parenting style and students' academic performance. Similarly, Okudo et al. (2023) found that a negative relationship exists between authoritarian parenting style and academic achievement. On the contrary, Mogadime et al. (2022) found no relationship between authoritarian parenting style and the academic performance of students. Rohaizad et al. (2018) also found no relationship between authoritarian parenting styles and academic performance in children. Many Asian cultures have authoritarian parenting, which places a strong emphasis on obedience and rigorous discipline (Laghari et. Al., 2024). This approach has been linked to children's excellent academic performance and favourable social results, but it may have a detrimental effect on their mental abilities and self-worth (Șițoiu & Pânișoară, 2023). In the opinion of Garcia et al. (2020), authoritarian parenting tends to be toward the extreme of the parental warmth spectrum, characterised by less emotion and greater command.

Conversely, permissive parents are strong in warmth, allowing autonomy, and encouraging, but weak in firm control, supervision, logic, and explanation (Sanvictores & Mendez, 2022). The findings of Singh and Sihag (2022) revealed that in India, permissive parenting has no significant impact on children's academic performance. Similarly, Gidado & Abubakar (2025) found no relationship between parenting style and academic achievement. Mogadime et al. (2022) also

revealed that a permissive parenting style does not significantly influence student performance. Obiunu (2018) supported these findings, suggesting that a significant relationship does not exist between permissive parenting style and academic performance of secondary school students. Dornbusch et al. (2017) reported a contrary view that permissive parenting methods have a significant impact on the academic performance of young people. Similarly, Bada and Pwajok (2020) found that the permissive parenting style has a positive impact on students' academic performance in schools. This contradiction in the review of the literature may be due to differences in social and cultural structures, which may also lead us to conclude that the effects of parenting practices might differ between nations.

Although numerous studies mentioned above have provided specific insights into the subject of children's parenting backgrounds, little is known about how parenting practices affect the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in North-West Nigeria. Furthermore, based on existing research, it is clear that the impact of parenting styles on academic performance in pre-primary in this region has not been well examined. This study, therefore, aims to fill this gap in the literature by focusing on the impact of parenting styles on academic performance among pre-primary school pupils in North-West Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Poor academic performance among pupils has captured the interest of researchers, educators, curriculum developers, policymakers in education, and government officials at all levels. A substantial number of the challenges that contribute to pupils performing poorly in school originate from their family settings; therefore, the need to investigate pupils' poor academic performances must begin with the parents at home, since it is one of the most potent drivers of education and obviously, the bedrock of any child. This is so because, prior to attending school, training begins at home, making the family the primary educational agency. Therefore, understanding the influence of parenting styles and the academic success of pre-primary school pupils in North West Nigeria becomes critical.

While considerable research has been devoted to examining parenting styles and academic performance in primary and secondary schools, there is a lack of empirical research on the effects of parenting approaches on academic Performance in North-west Nigeria. It is in the light of the aforementioned that the author takes an interest in examining the influence of parenting style and academic performance in pre-primary schools in North-West, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This research aims to investigate the impact of parenting style on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in the North West, Nigeria. Therefore, specific objectives are to:

- 1) Find out the influence of authoritarian parenting styles on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria.
- 2) Examine the influence of authoritative parenting styles on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria.
- 3) Determine the influence of permissive parenting styles on academic performance among pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to guide the researcher in the study:

- 1) To what extent do authoritarian parenting styles influence the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils?
- 2) To what extent do authoritative parenting styles influence the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils?
- 3) To what extent do permissive parenting styles influence the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: Authoritarian parenting styles have no significant influence on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils

H₀₂: Authoritative parenting styles have no significant influence on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils

H₀₃ Permissive parenting styles have no significant influence on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, a descriptive survey design was used. It is a methodology that gathers, examines, and interprets information collected from a sample believed to represent the total population, allowing for the study of a group of individuals or objects in their natural environments (Akpakwu, 2019). The adoption of 'descriptive survey design' is justified because, in a short amount of time, it enables comprehensive data collection on a broad population, identifying and reporting the current state of affairs (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). For this reason, just an adequate number of samples of the population have been drawn for analysis. The method is considered the most suitable for this research, as it aims to determine the influence of parenting styles on academic performance in pre-primary school pupils in North-west Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The research population consisted of all public pre-primary schools in the North-West region of Nigeria. The information available indicates that there is a total of nine thousand, three hundred and eighty-two (9,382) public pre-primary schools in the North West, Nigeria (FME, 2023). Thus, the population of the study covers all pupils in nursery three (3) drawn from public pre-primary schools in North-west, Nigeria, with a total population of one hundred and eighty-four thousand, six hundred and eighty-two (184,682) nursery three pupils (FME, 2023).

Sampling Size and Sampling Procedure

A sample size of three hundred and eighty-four (384) nursery three (3) pupils was used in the study using a proportionate random sampling technique. The justification for choosing this figure from this population aligns with Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) assertion that a total population of 232,766 yields a sample size of 384, as shown in the table. However, since the 384-sample size was the smallest, the researcher chose to expand it to 400 to reduce sampling error and increase the likelihood of generalisation.

A simple random sampling technique was also used to select two (2) pre-primary schools in each of the three (3) senatorial zones of the seven (7) states, making a total of 42 pre-primary schools. The justification for using a simple random sample was driven by the idea that every element in the overall population has an equal and distinct likelihood of being included in the sample. Similarly, caregivers of the forty (42) pre-primary schools selected will equally be sampled for the study. Additionally, a sample of 400 parents, one per each pre-primary school pupil, chosen from the 42 pre-primary schools sampled in North West, Nigeria, were sent a questionnaire in an envelope on behalf of the child to complete regarding their parenting styles.

Instrumentation

The study's instruments were validated, and a trial test was conducted to assess the reliability of the instruments. Data were gathered using a 37-item parenting style questionnaire developed by the researcher, which employed a four-point rating system. Similarly, to determine the pattern of academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in the North West, the academic records of pupils for the first and second terms of the 2024 academic session were collected and analysed.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The study's instruments were validated, and a trial test was conducted to assess the reliability of the instruments. Using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test, the researcher

obtained an index value of 0.79. This aligns with Mukherjee's (1995) proposition that the average value of the correlation coefficient should be approximately 0.70. Therefore, the instrument was reliable and internally consistent for the study.

Data Collection Procedure

After receiving permission from the headteachers of the schools, the inventory was conducted, and respondents were given ample time to finish the questionnaire. The researchers provided the respondents with the instrument immediately and detailed instructions on how to complete the questionnaires, which were then collected as soon as they were finished.

Method of Data Analysis

In analysing the data, the researcher used percentages, mean scores and standard deviations to answer the research questions. In addition, 'Analysis of Variance' (ANOVA) was also used to test the study hypotheses at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. The data were organised and prepared for analysis using the "Statistical Package for Social Sciences" (SPSS).

RESULTS

Demographic Data of the Respondents

In this section, the researcher presents data related to demographic characteristics, including respondents' gender and age.

Table 1: Questionnaire Distribution and Returned Rate

Returned/Not Returned	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Number of Returned	378	94.5
Number of Not Returned	22	5.5
Total Number Distributed	400	100.00

Table 1 shows that a total of 400 questionnaires were distributed, representing 100% of the sample. 378(94.50%) questionnaires were returned, while 22(5.50%) questionnaires were not returned. The

returned questionnaires constitute the total number of questionnaires to be analysed, hence they make up 100%.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	104	23.2	27.5	27.5
	Female	274	61.0	72.5	100.0
	Total	378	84.2	100.0	

Table 2 shows that 104 (27.5%) of the respondents were male pupils, while 274 (61%) were female pupils. This

indicates that there are more female participants than male participants in this study.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-2	2	.4	.5	.5
	3-4	69	15.4	18.3	18.8
	5-6	292	65.0	77.2	96.0
	7-above	15	3.3	4.0	100.0
	Total	378	84.2	100.0	

Table 3 shows that the ages of the respondents are 2(0,5%), 1–2 years, 69(18.3%), 3-4 years, 292(77.2%), 5-6 years, while 15(4%) are seven and above years. This implies that the majority of respondents are between the ages of 5 and 6.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Authoritarian parenting styles have no significant influence on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 4: ANOVA Computations on Authoritarian Parenting Style and Academic Performance of Pre-primary Pupils

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.451	3	.817	1.348	.258
Within Groups	226.618	374	.606		
Total	229.069	377			

A one-way ANOVA was calculated to investigate the influence of Authoritarian parenting style on academic performance. The findings in Table 4 indicate that there is no significant influence of parenting style on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils, as the p-value is greater than the critical value of 0.05 at the alpha level of 0.05. This indicates that Hypothesis 3, which claims that parenting styles have no significant

impact on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils, is accepted. The conclusion established reveals that parenting techniques have no significant effect on children's academic progress.

H₀₂: Authoritative parenting styles have no significant influence on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 5: ANOVA Computations on Authoritative Parenting Style and Academic Performance of Pre-primary Pupils

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	17.770	3	5.923	10.484	.000
Within Groups	211.299	374	.565		
Total	229.069	377			

A one-way ANOVA was calculated to investigate the influence of Authoritative parenting style on the academic performance of pupils. The findings in Table 5 indicate a significant influence of authoritative parenting style on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils, as the p-value is less than the critical value of 0.05 at the alpha level of 0.05. This indicates that Hypothesis 2, which claims that authoritative parenting styles have

no significant impact on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils, is rejected. The conclusion established reveals that authoritative parenting techniques have a significant effect on children's academic progress.

H₀₃: Permissive parenting styles have no significant influence on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria

Table 6: ANOVA Computations on Permissive Parenting Style and Academic Performance of Pre-primary Pupils

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	34.326	3	11.442	21.974	.000
Within Groups	194.743	374	.521		
Total	229.069	377			

A one-way ANOVA was calculated to investigate the influence of permissive parenting style on the academic performance of pupils. The findings in Table 6 indicate a significant influence of permissive parenting style on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils, as the p-value is less than the critical value of 0.05 at the alpha level. This indicates that Hypothesis 3, which claims that permissive parenting styles have no significant impact on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils, is rejected. The conclusion established reveals that permissive parenting techniques have a significant effect on children's academic progress.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study's findings showed that authoritarian parenting style has no significant influence on the academic

performance of pre-primary school pupils in the North-West region of Nigeria. This finding aligns with Mogadime et al. (2022), who found no relationship between authoritarian parenting styles and academic performance in children. Similar findings were reported by Obiunu (2018), who found no connection between children's academic achievement and an authoritarian parenting style. On the contrary, Laghari et al. (2024) found that the authoritarian parenting style has a harmful impact on the academic achievement of learners. This is in line with the body of research that indicates authoritarian parenting, that is typified by high expectations but poor responsiveness, is harmful to children's emotional and mental development. Thus, stakeholders should not focus too much emphasis on the

link between parental style and academic performance in pre-primary schools in North-West Nigeria.

Furthermore, an authoritative parenting style has a significant influence on the academic performance of pupils. In support of the above assertion, Singh and Sihag (2022) found that an authoritative parenting style has a positive impact on children's behaviour in schools. Additionally, Meremu and Idoko (2021) reported a similar result, showing that an authoritative parenting style had a favourable relationship with the academic achievement of senior secondary school students. Likewise, Noreen et al. (2021) also reveal that parents maintain a bond of affection and encouragement towards children, display attachment, place an emphasis on rules and regulations, deny children any degree of autonomy, refrain from spoiling them, and hold their children's hands tightly. It is therefore concluded that authoritative parents were very accommodating and responsive as they encouraged their children about the dangers associated with negative peer influence. On the contrary, Adeyemi (2022) revealed that teenagers of African American and Asian American descent found no indication of a beneficial influence of authoritative parenting style. The study led us to the conclusion that the effects of parenting practices might be different between nations.

Moreover, the study's results revealed that a permissive parenting style has a significant influence on learners' academic performance. The finding of Laghari et. al. (2024) concurs with the present finding, stating that permissive parenting has a negative impact on children's academic performance. Equally, Dornbusch et al. (2017) obtained a similar result, indicating that permissive parenting methods harm the academic performance of young people, which is likely due to the parents' lack of control and discipline over their children. This aligns with the current literature, which suggests that high levels of warmth and nurturance characterised a permissive style of parenting, moderate levels of communication, and low levels of disciplinary strategies and expectations of maturity and control, which tend to lead children toward lower academic performance.

These results highlight the crucial role that parenting practices play in influencing various aspects of pupils' development. While permissive and authoritarian parenting styles typically have a negative impact on these outcomes, authoritative

parenting is good for developing mental agility, confidence, and academic performance. The findings indicate that to promote the overall development of pupils in pre-primary schools in North West Nigeria, interventions that encourage authoritative parenting behaviours should be implemented.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were derived from the study's findings: analysis of the responses from the pupils' parents revealed that, contrary to expectations, authoritarian parenting styles had no significant influence on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils. Similarly, authoritative parenting style has no considerable impact on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in the North-West region of Nigeria.

Additionally, a permissive parenting style has no significant impact on the academic performance of pre-primary school pupils in the North-West region of Nigeria. This suggests that factors outside of parental influence can also have an impact on children's academic achievement. Given that authoritarian parenting practices have not been found to affect pupils' academic achievement, a comparable study could be conducted by incorporating additional variables that may influence performance. This could include the parents' financial situation, education, experience, salary level, and work status.

RECOMMENDATIONS

These results suggest that parenting styles-focused interventions may enhance students' intellectual and emotional development. Thus, stakeholders should not focus too much emphasis on the link between authoritarian parental style and academic performance in pre-primary schools in North-West Nigeria. To enhance student outcomes, educators, legislators, and community leaders should advocate for authoritative parenting practices which promote caring and supportive relations. Likewise, to raise understanding of the connections between parenting practices and pupils' academic achievements, educational gatherings or family seminars could be considered from various areas, including the private sector, and across all educational levels and age groups.

Additionally, it may be suggested that a long-term (longitudinal) study be conducted to investigate the

relationship between pupils' academic performance and parenting practices. Similarly, government-sponsored education programs, such as the family-centred curriculum, should be introduced. This can help parents become better instructors and role models to their children.

REFERENCES

Adaku, O. C. & Anayo A. D. (2021). Parenting Styles as Correlates of Academic Achievement of Upper Basic students in Business Studies in Umuahia South Local Government Area of Abia State. *African Journal of Educational Archives*, 7(1), 1-10.

Adeyemi, A. E. (2022). Parenting Styles and Social-Emotional Competence of Pre-School Children in Abuja, Nigeria. [Master's Thesis] University of Strathclyde, Glasgow.

Akpakwu, O. S. (2019). Influence of Politics on Personnel Management in Federal and State Universities in the North Central States of Nigeria. Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

Bada, S. O., & Pwajok, M. A. (2020). Influence of Parenting Styles on Students' Academic Performance for Education Quality Assurance in Selected Secondary Schools in Katsina Metropolis. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 18(1).

Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.

Dornbusch, S. M., Ritter, P. L., Lederman, P. H., Roberts, D. F., & Fraleigh, M. J. (2017). The Relation of Parenting Style to Adolescent Achievement. *Early Adolescence. Child Development*, 4 (8), 841–851.

Federal Ministry of Education (2023). *Education Sector Analysis of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, Assessing the Status of Education in the Federation and OAK States*. World Bank - IIEP-

UNESCO Dakar: Almadies – Route de Ngor BP 3311 Dakar – Senegal.

Gidado, B. K. & Abubakar, H. (2025). Correlation Between Parenting Styles and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*. Vol. 51(7), 474–485.

Gidado, B. K., & Anyio, B. T. (2025). Influence of parenting styles on conduct disorder among secondary school students in north-central Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research in Developing Areas*, 6(2), 55 - 67. <https://doi.org/10.47434/JEREDA.6.2.2025.55>.

Gidado, B. K., & Diffang, A. D. (2024). Relationships among home background factors, conduct disorder and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation (IJEE)*, 10, 2695-1940. <https://doi.org/10.56201/ijee.v1.no1.2024.pg487.497>.

Gidado, B. K., & Diffang, A. D. (2023). Family dysfunction and parental role abdication a predisposing factors for drug abuse among secondary school adolescents and youths in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Science & Humanities Research*. Vol. 06 Issue 06, 01-12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7998101>.

Hassan, M., Malik, A. S., Sang, G., Rizwan, M., Mushtaque, I., & Naveed, S. (2022). Examine the Parenting Style's Effect on the Academic Achievement Orientation of Secondary School Students: The Moderating Role of Digital Literacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13.

Janius, N., Ishar, M. I. M., Bang, P., Sid, R., & Wong, G. (2023). The Effects of Music towards the Mathematical Language Development of Children. *Malaysian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities (MJSSH)*, 8(4), e002249 e002249.

- Janius, N., Siti K. B. J., & Mohammad, A. A. (2024). Parenting Style and Academic Performance among Secondary Students in Kota Belud, Sabah. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 12(02), 907–929
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Table for determining sample size *Educational and Psychological Measurement Journal* 3 (6), 607-610. from a given population.
- Laghari, M. S N., Nawaz, S., Ahmad, I., & Mehmood, B. (2024). Impact of Parenting Style on Academic Achievement, Emotional Intelligence and Self-Esteem among University Students in Southern Punjab. *Journal of Policy Research*, 10(3), 77–82. <https://doi.org/10.61506/02.00321>
- Meremu, Y. & Idoko B. I. (2021). Relationship between Parenting Styles and Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Benue State. *Journal of Guidance and Counselling Studies*, 5(1), 225-233. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109178>
- Mogadime R. S., Som, P. B. & Moshe G. G. (2022). Parenting Styles and Learners' Performance: Evidence from Junior Secondary Schools in Botswana. *Canadian Journal of Educational and Social Studies*, Vol. 2(5), 1-16.
- Mukherjee, D. (1995). The relationship between socio-economic background and participation in education. ACEE Research Monograph, (1).
- National Commission for Colleges of Education (2020). Nigeria Certificate in Education Minimum Standard for Early Childcare and Education. NCCE, Abuja
- Noreen, H., Ahmad, M., & Shahzadi, U. (2021). Effect of Parenting Styles on Pupils' Academic Achievement at the Elementary Level. *Journal of Development and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 95–110.
- Obiunu, J. J. (2018). Influence of Parenting Styles on the Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Ethiopie East Local Government Area, Delta State. *Int. J. Educ. Technol. Learning*, 2(2), 54-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20448/2003.22.54.58>.
- Ogazie, C. A. & Arungwa, D. A. (2021). Parenting Styles as Correlates of Academic Achievement of Upper Basic Pupils in Business Studies in Umuahia South Local Government Area of Abia State. *African Journal of Educational Archives*, 7(1), 1–10. www.benchmarkjournal.com
- Okudo O. C. & Obumse N. A. (2022). Influence of Parenting Styles and Nurturance on the Psychosocial Development of Adolescents in Enugu State. Implications for employability and Global competitiveness. SGOJAHDS Vol. 5 (4).
- Okudo, O. C.; Obumse, N. A. & Okafor, O. S. (2023). Parenting Styles and Self-Efficacy as Correlates of Academic Achievements of Students in Public Secondary Schools of South-Eastern States of Nigeria. *Sapientia Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Development Studies*, Vol. 6(2), 143–153.
- Rohaizad, N. A. A. B., Rabi, N. B. M., Ghazali, N. H. B. C. M., Wahab, N. B. A., & Kosmin, M. (2018). The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Parenting Style on Students' Academic Achievement in Hulu Terengganu District. *Journal of Fundamental and Applied Sciences*, 10(3S), 7–18. <https://doi.org/10.4314/JFAS.V10:3S.7>
- Sanvictores, T., & Mendez, M. (2022, September 18). Types of parenting styles and effects on children. National Library of Medicine; Stat. Pearls Publishing.
- Singh, S. C. & Sihag, J. (2022). The Effects of Parenting Style on Children's Behaviour: A Systematic Literature Review in India. *The Pharma Innovation Journal: SP-11(11): 1695-1702*.

Șițoiu, A. & Pânișoară G. (2023). The Emotional Intelligence of Today's Parents – Influences on Parenting Style and Parental Competence. 11.

Steinberg, L. (2022). Adolescence (6th ed.). Boston, MA: McGraw-Hill.

Tanko, L. (2025). Influence of Parenting Styles on Conduct Disorder in Pre-Primary Schools in North-West, Nigeria. In: E. T. Ajibade. (Ed.) Book of Education and Social Transformation: International Approaches (pp. 83–100). Farabi Publishing House, Ankara.